

A Comparative Study on the Performances of Q-Learning and Neural Q-Learning Agents toward Analysis of Emergence of Communication

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Abstract: In this paper, we suppose the gesture theory that is one theory on the origin of language, which tries to establish that speech originated from gestures. Based on the theory, we assume that “actions” having some purposes can be used as “symbols” in the communication through a learning process. The purpose of this study is to clarify what abilities of agents and what conditions are necessary to acquire usages of the actions as the symbols. To investigate them, we adopt a collision avoidance game and compare the performances of Q-learning agents with that of Neural Q-learning agents. In our simulation, we found that the Neural Q-learning agent’s ability to reach the goal place is higher than the Q-learning agent’s one. In contrast, the Neural Q-learning agent’s ability to avoid collisions is lower than the Q-learning agent’s one. If the inconsistencies in the learning data sets of the Neural Q-learning agent, however, can be resolved, the agent has enough potential to improve its ability for collision avoidance. Therefore, we conclude that the most suitable agent to analyze the emergence of communication is the Neural Q-learning agent who changed a feed forward type neural network into a recurrent type neural network that can resolve the inconsistencies in the learning data sets.

Keywords: Q-learning, Neural Q-learning, Collision Avoidance Game, Reinforcement Learning Agents, Multi-Agent System.

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, we are communicating with each other by using various media such as voices, characters, and gestures. A proto-communication, however, would have been simpler than the present communication. How does the communication emerge and evolve to complex form like a current one? To answer the above questions, Corballis [1] and Tomasello [2] claim that gestures using hands and arms precede voices in the evolution of communication. This is well known as the gesture theory.

There are many researches concerning the emergence of communication. Takano and Arita [3] conducted an evolutionary simulation experiment in which agents play a collision avoidance game. The experiment showed that a cooperative behavior that informs a collision avoidance behavior through mutual refusing eye contact emerged, although no rewards have been given for the success of the communication. The model adopted in the experiment that the agents were adjusted by evolution.

With the emergence of the actual communication; however, we think that some methods and knowledge needed for the success of the communication do not have congenitally and are obtained by a heuristic learning after birth.

Unlike the research of Takano and Arita [3], Shirasaki and Sato [4] adopted the collision avoidance task with Q-learning agents [5], but an action using eyesight to avoid collision with opponents was not observed. The reason why this result was given can be presumed that the environmental information given to the agents is discretized in the Q-learning [5], and differences of important states to achieve the agents’ aims can be overlooked by the discretization.

Moreover, Sato [6] adopted a modified model of Shirasaki and Sato [4] which can take into account the past information earned from the opponents, and confirmed that more appropriate behavior can be obtained by the modified one. From this result, our concern was whether or not there is a factor having an effect on the agent’s learning except for the past information reference.

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In accord with the above background, we hypothesize that the communication can be established by the following process; “actions” having some purposes would be used as “symbols” on the communication through the action learning and interaction between opponents in the emergence of communication.

The purpose of this study is to discuss the requirements of the reinforcement learning agents suitable for analyzing the emergence of communication and for verifying our hypothesis. For realizing the settings that are close to the real environment, we adopt a Neural Q-learning [7][8] that can treat continuous quantity of input information. Also, we compare the performances of the Q-learning [5] agents with that of the Neural Q-learning [7][8] agents which become platforms to consider how “actions” is used as “symbols” through the collision avoidance game similar to the model of Takano and Arita [3] and to investigate its necessary conditions and factors.

II. COLLISION AVOIDANCE GAME

In our simulation, we use a multi-agent system based on the model of Takano and Arita [3], because it is suitable for verifying our hypothesis in which “actions” with certain purposes come to use as “symbols” on the communication. In the multi-agent system of our study, many agents are randomly placed in two-dimensional continuous space surrounded by the wall and aimed to attain their goals from each starting point as soon as possible. When the agent collides with the opponents, the movement velocity of the agent at the next step is decreased drastically. Because of that, the agent is required not only to approach to its goal but also to expect the behavior of the nearest neighbor agent and to avoid collision with the others. After the agent arrived at its goal, its new goal is randomly replaced. We named the game “Collision Avoidance Game.” The schematic view of the game is shown in Fig.1.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the agent used in our simulation have a fun shape type eyesight, R , face type two wheels, and can move its eyesight from side to side. The agent moves by receiving the following eight information; the goal (d_g, θ_g), the angle of direction of its eye (Φ), the nearest agent in its own eyesight ($d_a, \theta_a, \alpha, \beta$), and wall (d_w), where d_g is the distance of the goal, θ_g is the angle of the goal to the direction of movement, α is the angle of direction of the nearest neighbor agent's movement to the direction that the agent watched opponent, β is the angle of direction of the

nearest neighbor agent's eyesight to the direction that the agent watched opponent, and d_w is the distance of the nearest neighbor wall.

Fig. 1 Schematic view of a collision avoidance game and information given to the agents.

Depending on the above inputs, the agent outputs an angular velocity, $\Delta\Phi(t)$, and two wheels' tread velocities, $w_r(t)$ and $w_l(t)$, where $w_r(t)$ and $w_l(t)=0.1$ or 1.0 , $-\pi/2 < \Phi \leq \pi/2$, $\Delta\Phi = -\pi/50.0, 0.0$, or $\pi/50.0$. The agent's directions of its movement and eye at the next step are calculated based on $w_r(t)$ and $w_l(t)$ as the following formulas.

$$\phi(t + 1) = \phi(t) + \Delta\phi(t) \quad (1)$$

$$m(t + 1) = m(t) + \frac{w_r(t) - w_l(t)}{2r} \quad (2)$$

where m is the direction of movement, r is the radius of the agent. The migration velocity of the agent, v , is calculated as below.

$$v(t) = \frac{w_r(t) + w_l(t)}{2} \quad (3)$$

where v is given the following cost, depending on the size of Φ .

$$v(t) = v(t)(-c|\phi| + 1) \quad (4)$$

where c is the size of cost ($c \geq 0$), and also v is set to 0 when $v < 0$. We can hereby give the following two costs; one is the explicit cost that the migration velocity decreases depending on the measure of the angle of movement direction away from the direction of the eye, and the other is the implicit cost that the agent becomes difficult to realize the appropriate collision avoidance behavior because the agent becomes difficult to bring the others into its sight by turning its sight away from other agents. Moreover, the velocity of the agent's movement at the next step is drastically decreased when colliding with the others to represent the situation

where the agents become to be not able to move by receiving a shock from colliding with each other. Each agent's coordinates at the next step, $x(t+1)$ and $y(t+1)$, are given by the following formulas.

$$x(t + 1) = x(t) + v(t) \cos m(t + 1) \quad (5)$$

$$y(t + 1) = y(t) + v(t) \sin m(t + 1) \quad (6)$$

Next, we explain the learning methods. In a situation in which symbols and forms used in a communication are not established, we assume that the agent obtains a way of communication by trial and error. Also, there is a possibility that the differences of the important states to achieve the aim can be overlooked in the case of discretizing the environment information. Based on the above explanations, we adopt the Neural Q-learning [7][8] which is the hybridization between two systems; one is the Q-learning [5] that is one of the learning by trial and error, the other is the neural network [9] which can treat continuous values as inputs.

The Q-learning [5] is one of the reinforcement learning method by trial and error. In accordance with the following equation, the agents with the Q-learning renew the Q-values representing the worth of the agents' actions for each state on the environment, and obtain more appropriate behaviors.

$$Q(s(t), a(t)) := Q(s(t), a(t)) + \eta_Q [rw(t + 1) + \gamma \max_a Q(s(t + 1), a) - Q(s(t), a(t))] \quad (7)$$

where $a(t)$ is an action conducted at time t , $Q(s(t), a(t))$ is a Q-value for an action conducted under a state s at time t , η_Q is the learning rate, $rw(t+1)$ is a reward given from the environment when conducting an action under a state s , and γ is the discount rate.

The neural network [9] is a learning model simulated features of the human brains. In this study, we adopt the feed forward type neural network (FFNN) in which the input data flow only one way to the output layer.

In the Neural Q-learning [7][8], the observed data (continuous data) of the environment as the input is given to the FFNN first. Next, the Q-values for each action corresponding to all output neurons is gotten from the FFNN. Finally, the agents get rewards after conducting their actions based on the Q-values. The instructor signals are generated by using the following equation.

$$T(s(t), a(t)) := rw(t + 1) + \gamma \max_a Q(s(t + 1), a) \quad (8)$$

where $T(s(t), a(t))$ is the renewed Q-value for the action conducted under a state s at time t and is also an instructor signal used for the BP learning of the FFNN. Except for the valuables explained here, the remained ones of the equation (8) are the same as the valuables of the equation (7). The agents learn to be able to presume more appropriate Q-values by using the instructor signals. As well as the Q-learning, the ϵ -greedy policy [5] is adopted as the way of behavior selection. A procedure of the Neural Q-learning is shown in Fig. 2. The numbers in Fig. 2 mean the order of processing.

Fig. 2 A procedure for the Neural Q-learning.

III. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

A. Settings of simulation experiments

The parameters used in the simulation experiments are as follows: The rewards (positive values) and penalties (negative values) giving to the agents are +0.12 when arriving at their goals, -0.01 when colliding with the opponents included the wall, and getting close to the wall. Moreover, the reward given to the agent every step is (the past d_a - the current d_a) \times 0.08. Also -0.03 \times $\pi/2.0 \times |\pi|$ is given to the agent as the penalty when the agent's eye averted from the direction of its movement, and is used for the learning of only output concerning its eye movement. The simulation experiments are conducted in a two-dimensional continuous space measuring 20 by 20. The number of agents is 3. The collision avoidance game is continuously played until 10000 episodes, where one episode consists of 10000 steps.

The agent is represented by a round shape with a radius r of 0.5, and has an eyesight R which is a fan shape with a radius of 5 and the angle π centered at the eyesight. The cost averted from the direction of the agent's eyesight is 0.5. When the agent came into collision with the opponent, its movement speed at the next step multiplies by 0.05.

Here are the parameters of the reinforcement learning; the probability ϵ to select an action randomly is 0.1, the learning rate η_Q is 0.01, and the discount rate γ is 0.8. Also, the parameters of the FFNN are as

follow; the learning rate η_N is 0.01, and the strength of non-linearity λ is 0.8. The learning process of the FFNN is completed when the learning error dropped below 0.01. The FFNN has eight input neurons, five hidden neurons, and seven output neurons. The seven values of the output neurons correspond to four values ($w_r, w_l = 0.1$ or 1.0) for actions to move the agent's two wheels and three values ($\Delta\Phi = -\pi/50.0, 0.0, \text{ or } \pi/50.0$) for actions to move the agent's eye from side to side.

In this study, we use one type of the Q-learning agent and six types of the Neural Q-learning agents. The Neural Q-learning agents have two types of the largest number of learning iterations (10 or 100) and three sizes of memories (1, 3, or 5). The largest number of learning iterations is an upper limit of the number to learn all patterns. The memory size is the amount of information for past multiple steps, which the agents learn them every step. We conducted the simulation experiments with ten different kinds of random seeds per seven types of agents and showed ensemble averages of simulation results for the last 1000 episodes in all runs as the results of each agent.

B. Results of simulation experiments

First, as illustrated in Fig. 3~5, we show the comparative results of ensemble averages of the number of times of collisions with the opponents per one agent every episode in the Q-learning and the Neural Q-learning agents with several different maximum numbers of learning. Figures 3~5 are the results in cases that the memory sizes of the Neural Q-learning agents are 1, 3, and 5, respectively.

Fig. 3 Ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents per one agent at each episode when the Neural Q-learning agents have their memory size 1.

As can be seen in Fig. 3~5, the number of times of collisions of the Neural Q-learning agents in each case of the memory size is larger than that of the Q-learning

agents. In case that the memory size is 1 as depicted in Fig. 3, the number of times of collisions of the Neural Q-learning agents whose the maximum number of learning is 100 is less than the agents whose the maximum number of learning is 10 relatively. In contrast, in cases that the memory sizes are 3 and 5 as shown in Fig. 4 and 5, the results of them are almost the same.

Fig. 4 Ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents per one agent at each episode when the Neural Q-learning agents have their memory size 3.

Fig. 5 Ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents per one agent at each episode when the Neural Q-learning agents have their memory size 5.

Along with Fig. 3~5, the comparative results of ensemble averages of the number of times of collisions with the others per an agent every episode in the Q-learning and the Neural Q-learning agents with several different memory sizes are shown in Fig. 6 and 7. Figures 6 and 7, however, are the results in cases that the maximum number of learning of the Neural Q-learning agents are 10 and 100, respectively.

As can be seen in Fig. 6 and 7, the number of times of collisions of the Neural Q-learning agents whose memory size is 1 is the lowest in both cases that the

maximum numbers of learning are 10 and 100. The numbers of times of collisions in cases that the memory sizes are 3 and 5 are almost the same. Therefore, there is a little difference between the Neural Q-learning agents whose memory sizes are 3 and 5.

Fig. 6 Ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents per one agent at each episode when the maximum number of learning of the Neural Q-learning agents is 10.

Fig.7 Ensemble averages of the number of times colliding with the opponents per one agent at each episode when the maximum number of learning of the Neural Q-learning agents is 100.

Next, as illustrated in Fig. 8~10, we depict the comparative results of ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals per one agent every episode in the Q-learning and the Neural Q-learning agents with several different maximum numbers of learning. Figures 8~10 are the results in cases that the memory sizes of the Neural Q-learning agents are 1, 3, and 5, respectively.

Figure 8 shows that the number of times arriving at the goals of the Q-learning agents whose memory size is 1 is less than that of the Neural Q-learning agents. The results of two types of the Neural Q-learning agents are almost the same, though the maximum numbers of learning are different. But, the results of the Neural Q-

learning agents whose memory sizes are 3 and 5 as illustrated in Fig. 9 and 10 are almost identical to or less than that of the Q-learning agent. The result of the Neural Q-learning agent whose memory size is 100 is also less than that of the one whose memory size is 10. In addition, as the memory size increases, the difference between the results of the Neural Q-learning agents in cases that the maximum numbers of learning are 10 and 100 comes to increase.

Fig. 8 Ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals per one agent at each episode when the Neural Q-learning agents have their memory size 1.

Fig. 9 Ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals per one agent at each episode when the Neural Q-learning agents have their memory size 3.

Fig. 10 Ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals per one agent at each episode when the Neural Q-learning agents have their memory size 5.

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As with Fig. 8~10, the comparative results of ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals per one agent every episode in the Q-learning and the Neural Q-learning agents with several different memory sizes are shown in Fig. 11 and 12, which are the results in cases that the maximum number of learning of the Neural Q-learning agents are 10 and 100, respectively.

Fig. 11 Ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals per one agent at each episode when the maximum number of learning of the Neural Q-learning agents is 10.

Fig. 12 Ensemble averages of the number of times arriving at the goals per one agent at each episode when the maximum number of learning of the Neural Q-learning agents is 100.

As indicated in Fig. 11 and 12, we confirmed that the number of times arriving at the goals of the Neural Q-learning agents whose memory size is 1 is the largest in all other agent models. As the memory size increases, the number of times arriving at the goals of the Neural Q-learning agents are decreased. This difference of performances of each Neural Q-learning agent in case that the maximum number of learning is 100 is larger than that of the agents in case that the maximum

number of learning is 10.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Comparison Q-learning with Neural Q-learning

First, we confirmed that the Q-learning agents have high collision avoidance capabilities in the collision avoidance game. This is assuming that the agents could relatively easily avoid collisions with others by only discretized rough information whether or not the traveling direction of the nearest neighbor agent in the region of its own eye angled oneself, the opponent got close to oneself than the past step, and so on. Or due to receiving discretized environmental states as inputs, there is a possibility that the Q-learning agents is easier to learn more effectively collision avoidance behaviors than the Neural Q-learning agents whose states are given as continuous values.

On the other hand, in the Neural Q-learning processes, the environmental information which can be observed are overwhelmingly large as compared to the Q-learning, because the continuous values as the inputs are given. In the Q-learning and the Neural Q-learning, the agents can obtain the most appropriate behaviors through repeatedly trying various actions at each state. Thus, as the states are increased, the agents become less able to try to estimate many combinations of states and actions. The Neural Q-learning, therefore, is more difficult to obtain the effective behaviors than the Q-learning agents. Moreover, when avoiding collisions with the others, the opponents are not always the same, so that it is easier to occur inconsistencies that different actions are appropriate although the agents are in the same states. That is to say, the Neural Q-learning agents have the following two difficulties, 1) one is the difficulty to obtain appropriate behaviors caused by huge states which can be observed, and 2) the other is the difficulty to completely learn circumstances including some inconsistencies, so that it is gathered from these difficulties that the agents could not decrease the number of times of collisions as the results.

Next, it was shown that the ability to arrive at the goals of the Neural Q-learning agent is superior to that of the Q-learning. This result is thought to be due to need of correct information of angles and distances to the goals. In the case of the Q-learning agents, such necessary information to arrive at the goals is simplified by discretizing them, so that it is assumed that the agents cannot learn and obtain appropriate behaviors that can arrive at the goals. In contrast, the Neural Q-learning agents have a difficulty to obtain appropriate

behaviors but can correctly get distance and angles of the goals as continuous values. Also, the coordinates of the goals are fixed until the agents arrive at them, so that the resembled behaviors are easily judged as being appropriate again in the similar states. Thus, it is thought that the Neural Q-learning agents could relatively easily learn to obtain the behaviors.

B. Comparison with Various Combinations of Parameters in Neural Q-learning

Let us see the comparative results of influences by three types of memory sizes. In both of the numbers of times colliding with others and arriving at the goals, the Neural Q-learning agents whose memory size is 1 show the best performances, then, memory sizes 3 and 5 are the 2nd and the 3rd ranks, respectively. That is to say; as the memory size increases, the performance decreases. This is thought that the system adopted in this study is the feed forward type neural network which cannot appropriately learn a time series data with temporal structures, so that the network cannot correctly learn the past information and conveniently use the information. In the case that the memory size is larger than 1, it becomes difficult that the network learns the data sets with inconsistencies, where different behaviors are appropriate, though a present state is similar to the state experienced by the network in the past step.

Next, we compare with influences by the maximum number of learning. In the task of collision avoidance, it was not seen the differences of performances, even if the agents are set to the different maximum number of learning. In contrast, the number of times arriving at the goals, when the memory sizes are 3 and 5, were decreased. As mentioned above, the network comes to be difficult to learn when the memory sizes are 3 and 5. Therefore, even though the network repeats a lot of learning at once, it cannot learn appropriately. And to make things worse, its many iterations result in destruction of the network.

Sato [6] also discussed influences by referring to the past information. As well as the results observed in our simulations, in his research, it was shown that the performances of agents with only Q-learning are decreased because the agents cannot effectively treat temporal structures in inputs given from their environment.

C. Agent Suitable for Analysis of Emergent Phenomena of Communication

We made the hypothesis about the emergence of communication by a gesture, where “actions” with

some purposes can be used as “signals” on the communication. In the case of applying the collision avoidance game used in our study to the hypothesis, we can draw the following scenario; while the agents avoid collision with the opponents and quickly arrive at their goals, “an action” like a moving direction of eye would be used as “a signal” for the collision avoidance with each other, and their times of collisions can be decreased. Therefore, in order to analyze the emergent phenomena of communication and to verifying the hypothesis, it is thought that focusing on the ability of collision avoidance is important. Additionally, if the agents appropriately avoid collision with the opponents, they can minimize a slowdown in the speed of movement, so that the number of times arriving at the goals would be increased. That is to say; we need to consider not only the number of times of collisions but also the number of times arriving at the goals.

Let us pay attention to the ability of collision avoidance. From the simulation results, the agents with Q-learning can be said to be suitable for verifying our hypothesis. However, to realize the communication observed in the study of Takano and Arita [3], the agents must be able to learn the behaviors that order determined, where firstly informing direction of its own movement to the opponent by moving direction of its own sight line, and secondly moving to its direction informed at the past step, whereas it is difficult for the agents with Q-learning to obtain such behaviors with ordinal structure. Furthermore, to improve the number of times arriving at the goals by the agents with Q-learning, it is necessary to increase the number of environmental information that the agents can receive, but in the case of this, it becomes difficult to learn the information by the explosion of combination of the actions and the environmental states. Thus, we think that the Q-learning agents are not suitable for analyzing the emergence of communication and for evaluating our hypothesis.

By contrast, the Neural Q-learning agents was superior in the task of arriving at the goals, but their abilities of collision avoidance have no advantage over the Q-learning agents' ones. If a recurrent type neural network (RNN) having recurrent connections from the output or the hidden layers to the input layers, however, is adopted instead of the FFNN adopted in our study, the network can obtain behaviors with order. Also, if the RNN, the inconsistency concerned in the collision avoidance can be recognized as one pattern composed of many behaviors, so that learning data sets including such inconsistency can be succeeded. Moreover, referring to the past information resulted in the

deterioration of performance, but the RNN can appropriately treat a time-series data having temporal structure, so that we can hold promise that the agents with RNNs can obtain effective behaviors by utilizing the past information.

From the above, it is thought that the Neural Q-learning agents replaced by the RNNs are suitable for analyzing the emergence of communication and for verifying our hypothesis.

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study was to investigate the important requirements of the reinforcement learning agents suitable for verifying our hypothesis that the communication can be established by the following process; “actions” with some aims would be used as “symbols” on the communication through the action learning and interaction between opponents in the emergence of communication, and for analyzing such emergent phenomena. For the purpose, we have compared one type of the Q-learning agent with six types of the Neural Q-learning agents having different memory sizes and the maximum number of learning.

Consequently, it was shown that the Q-learning agents had high performances in the task of collision avoidance and the Neural Q-learning agents had high performance in the task of arriving at the goals. This is thought that the collisions could be avoided by using rough information about the other agents, and arriving at the goals was needed to obtain an accurate information about distances and angles of the goals. Moreover, in the Neural Q-learning, the agents whose memory sizes are 1 showed the highest performances in both of the tasks of avoiding collisions and arriving at the goals. As the reason for these, it is thought to be due to that the FFNN adopted in our study cannot appropriately learn a time-series data with temporal structures, and also, as the learned contents complexify by increasing the past information that the agents receive, the inconsistencies in the data come to occur easily.

From the features of each agent observed in our simulations, we evaluated the necessary requirements of agents to improve both of the abilities of avoiding collisions and arriving at the goals. Based on the outcome of the discussions mentioned above, we conclude that the Neural Q-learning agents which replaced the FFNN with the RNN are better suited for analyzing the emergent phenomena of communication by gesture and evaluating our hypothesis.

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